

Vaccine Development 10x faster through Open Sharing of Sars-Cov-2 Sequencing Data

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1. Background

Open sharing of Sars-Cov-2 sequencedata via Open Data platforms & registries has speed up vaccine development from 10-15 years to 10 months-1.5 years^{1a}

+6 mln sequences uploaded in COVID-19 Data portal since Jan 2021^{1b}

2. Global collaborations to publicly share CoV19 sequence data

- GISAID EpiCovplatform²
- European COVID-19 Data Platform (EMBL-EBI): connect platforms & registries
- COVID-19 Data Index: collects all types of CoV19 datasets
- Many more: NCBI Sars-Cov-2 Resources page, INSDC, ...

3. Rapid sharing of diverse data outputs challenges interoperability³

RDA COVID-19 WG CC BY

4. FAIR & Interoperable sharing of sequencedata⁴

Metadata

- RDA CoV19 recommendations & guidelines on data sharing
- Catalogues of CoV19 data sharing: Fairsharing.org etc.

Open Source Software

- Open Source Bioinformatics tools NextStrain, NextClade etc. use GISAID Data to enable visualisations

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Protocols

- ARTIC standard protocol for CoV19 WGS on the Oxford Nanopore Technologies sequencing platforms
- CDCs Advanced Molecular Detection SPHERES consortium standardize sequencing, (meta)data standards, accelerate data sharing etc.
- ➔ GitHub page: protocols, tools & resources for CoV19 WGS on various platforms (Illumina, PacBio etc.)

5. Timeline of CoV19 vaccine development & genomicdata availability⁵

Currently and as of 26th April 2023, there have been 764,474,387 confirmed cases of COVID-19, including 6,915,286 deaths, reported to WHO. As of 24 April 2023 a total of 13,325,228,015 vaccine doses have been administered.⁶

References

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Abbreviations

- ARTIC: Advancing Real-Time Infection Control Network
- CDC: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
- EMBL-EBI: European Molecular Biology Laboratory -European Bioinformatics Institute
- GISAID EpiCoV: Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data EpiCov platform
- GenBank: Genetic sequence database by the National Institutes of Health USA
- In silico: Experiment via computer simulation
- INSDC: International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
- NextStrain: Real-time tracking of pathogen evolution open source project
- NextClade: Open source tool that performs genetic sequence alignment for viruses
- RDA: Research Data Alliance
- RCD: Randomized clinical trials
- SPHERES: SARS-CoV-2 Sequencing for Public Health Emergency Response, Epidemiology and Surveillance
- WGS: whole genome sequencing